

A Theory without Space & Time

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Abstract:

Einstein would have liked a theory with no space and no time; he added that he didn't know how to do it (Klein & Spiro, 1996). I guess that Einstein was not excited by the job, all the more that getting rid of space and time requires having accurate definitions beforehand. This is the case today, but, if it's quite easy to proceed, we can't ensure that the replacement leads to significant progress in the theory. It's no doubt paradoxical that Einstein never defined time

and space, neither did contemporary researchers like Stephen Hawking. The lack of definitions about space and time is a real disadvantage, insofar as defining something is saying what it is; otherwise, we don't know what we're talking about. For example, what is the physical nature of space as such? What are the physical properties of time? Is time a phenomenon or a concept? In addition, a good definition is supposed to bring some theoretical extensions. For this purpose, the definitions of the second and the meter will be clarified; the signification of the covariance of the parameters in a relativistic situation will be reminded. Our target, getting rid of time and space, is based on two ideas:

- Given that the international unit of time is defined in relation to the frequency of the cesium, the term which is related to time will be replaced by a term related to the frequency.
- The cesium wavelength is a fundamental constant; it's of course covariant. It turns out that any length is proportional to the cesium wavelength; the proportionality coefficient, which is a multiple of the cesium wavelength, is invariant. The splitting in two parts is not only an arithmetical trick, it allows circumscribing the covariance.

Keywords: *Relativity, space, space-time, time.*

The Space & Time Dichotomy

During any research about space and time, we face an impressive dichotomy.

The word dichotomy (from the Greek *dikha*: in two, and *tomos*: portion) is often replaced by the word dialectics (from the Greek *dialectiké*: the art of discussion). Their proper meanings are completely different: dialectics is a study of a topic through an in-depth discussion, whereas dichotomy is a study of two subjects, based on comparison, opposition, relation.

As an illustration, we can state that the dialectics of time is as abundant as it is childish and erroneous; we can say that the dialectics of space is practically non-existent; yet, we observe that the dichotomy between space and time has had a tremendous development since the invention of the concept of velocity (5th century BCE) (Before Common Era) to the concept of space-time in Special Relativity in 1905.

Velocity

The Greek historians, Herodotus (484-425) in *“The Histories”* (Book I, 203; Book II, 6, 19 & 31) and Thucydides (c.465-c.395) in *“The Peloponnesian War”* (II, 97) use *“The walk per day”*, *“The navigation per day”* and *“The navigation per month”*; *“walk”* and *“navigation”* mean *“what has been travelled”* in one day or one month: these two prestigious authors Barguet, A. (1964) and Thucydide. (1964) invented velocity by unknowingly combining space and time.

Total walk = (walk per day) x (number of days)

A uniform motion in classical physics, provided that the words are defined, reads:

Distance travelled = (speed) x (duration of the travel)

Given that distance (space), duration (time) and speed, are not defined by the BIPM (2022), we are faced with a theoretical difficulty that must be resolved one way or another.

The Second

Definition of the second according to the BIPM in its SI Brochure updated in 2022:

« The second ... is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of the caesium frequency, $\Delta\nu_c$, the unperturbed ground-state hyperfine transition frequency of the caesium 133 atom, to be 9 192 631 770 when expressed in the unit Hz, which is equal to 1/s.

The effect of this definition is that the second is the duration of 9 192 631 770 periods of the radiation corresponding to the transition between the two hyperfine levels of the ground state of the caesium 133 atom » (BIMP, 2022).

- We dispute that “Hz” is equal to “1/s”: instead, “Hz” is equal to “cycle/s”.
- Defining the second in relation with the inverse of the second, is a sophism.
- The “period” is the “duration of a cycle”; therefore, “the duration of 9 192 631 770 durations of a cycle” is a sophism: “period” should be replaced by “cycle”.

Cycle is a measurable phenomenon, whereas “second” is a concept.

Hence a wording without “duration” and “period”, and with no referring to the inverse of the second:

« The second corresponds to 9 192 631 770 cycles of the radiation corresponding to the transition between the two hyperfine levels of the ground state of the caesium 133 atom ».

The Meter

Definition of the meter according to the BIPM updated in 2022:

« The metre ... is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of the speed of light in vacuum, c , to be 299 792 458 when expressed in the unit m/s, where the second is defined in terms of the caesium frequency $\Delta\nu_c$.

The effect of this definition is that one metre is the length of the path travelled by light in vacuum during a time interval with duration of 1/299 792 458 of a second » (BIMP, 2022).

- The words “length”, “time” and “duration” should not be used, as long as they are not defined.
- Given that the speed of light is an invariant fundamental constant, the speed should possess its own unit (“cel” instead of “m/s”); then $c = 299\,792\,458$ cel.
- The definition of the meter in relation with the speed of light, which is expressed in “meter” is a sophism.
- The definition of the meter in relation with “second” aggregates space to time, what is disputable. In the Relativity, space and time are components of space-time, admittedly covariant, but independent of each other.

The term $c/\Delta\nu_c$ is the wavelength λ_c (Greek letter *lambda*), which is a fundamental constant:

$$\lambda_c = c/\Delta\nu_c$$

$$\lambda_c = (299\,792\,458 \text{ cel}/9\,192\,631\,770 \text{ Hz})$$

$$\lambda_c = (299\,792\,458/9\,192\,631\,770) \text{ cel/Hz}$$

The term “cel/Hz” corresponds to the international unit “m”:

$$\lambda_c = (299\,792\,458 / 9\,192\,631\,770) \text{ m} \approx 0,0326122 \text{ m}$$

Therefore:

$$1\text{m} = (9\,192\,631\,770 / 299\,792\,458) \lambda_c \approx 30.663319 \lambda_c$$

Hence a wording without “second” and “length”:

« The meter is a unit equal to $(9\,192\,631\,770 / 299\,792\,458)$ times the cesium wavelength λ_c , which is approximately $30.663319 \lambda_c$ » (Dassonville, 2012).

Another wording can be suggested:

«The meter is what separate two positions of a photon (or an EM wave) after 30.663319 cycles of a cesium atom».

Both definitions of the second and the meter are written in relation with fundamental constants.

We don't need one to define the other: there is no theoretical connections between these two units, as well as between space and time.

The Baguette of Einstein

In classical physics, the values of parameters which describe a system (such as length, size, lifetime, speed) are invariant: it means that the values received by the observer are the same as the values emitted by the system.

Example with Einstein walking towards the bakery at speed “v” (Figure 1). As usual, the length of the image of the baguette received by Einstein is equal to the length of the image emitted by the baguette

All parameters are invariant during the travel of the image from the reference system of the baguette to that of Einstein.

Note that the image of the baguette travels to Einstein at the speed of light «». ».

**Figure 1. Invariance of Parameters:
The Value Received is Equal to the Value Emitted**

When the two reference systems move from each other at a relativistic speed “v”, the parameters are no more invariant. As an example, if the speed is equal to « $c/2$ » (half of light speed) (Figure 2), the baguette seems to

Einstein shorter: 41 cm instead of 47 cm. We observe a contraction of the lengths, a dilatation of durations and masses, etc.; all the parameters are covariant, except the light speed, which is invariant.

The phenomenon caused by the relativistic speed between the two reference systems, is reciprocal: Einstein seems smaller to the baker: 1m47 instead of 1m70.

By cons, there are seven baguettes in the window, and Einstein sees the seven baguettes; the relativistic context does not modify the number of baguettes: it is invariant.

Figure 2. Covariance of the Lengths: the Baguette Seems Shorter to Einstein. Einstein Seems Shorter to the Baker

The invariance is restored thanks to a concept called *space-time elementary interval* « ds », which is a mathematical combination of space « dl » and time « dt », such as:

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2) \quad (1)$$

A Theory with No Space and No Time

Now that space and time are defined, their nature and properties are identified, it's about expressing the equation (1) with no space and no time, according to the wish of Einstein.

- Replacing time “ dt ”:

The number of cycles (and/or cycle fragment) “ dn ” of an alternative system of frequency “ ν ” (Greek letter ν), written in elementary form, reads:

$$dn = \nu dt$$

Therefore, the duration “ dt ” of the event, in relation to the number of cycles, reads:

$$dt = dn / \nu$$

The duration “ dt ” of a phenomenon is given by the number of cycles “ dn ”, between the start and the end of the event.

Example when the clock indicates $dn = 919\,263\,177$ cycles:

Then, $dt = 91\,926\,3177 \text{ cycles} / 919\,263\,177 \text{ Hz} = 0.1 \text{ s}$ (a tenth of a second)

According to the BIPM, the accuracy of the cesium clock is between 10^{-15} et 10^{-16} .

- Replacing lengths:

The lengths “ dx ”, “ dy ” and “ dz ” are expressed as multiple and sub-multiple of the cesium wavelength “ λ_c ”:

$$dx = \lambda_c dk_x$$

$$dy = \lambda_c dk_y$$

$$dz = \lambda_c dk_z$$

Example: if $dk_x = 0.663319$, then $dx \approx (0.663319 / 30.663319) \text{ m} \approx 0.0216323 \text{ m}$

The “dk” numbers are invariant, like the number of baguettes in the window of Einstein bakery.

In the equation (1), we replace « dt » by « dn/v »; « dx » by « $\lambda_c dk_x$ »; etc.

The invariant elementary interval is such as:

. In the reference frame of the baker:

$$ds^2 = dn^2 c^2/v^2 - (dk_x^2 + dk_y^2 + dk_z^2) \lambda_c^2$$

. In the reference frame of Einstein:

$$ds'^2 = dn^2 c^2/v'^2 - (dk_x'^2 + dk_y'^2 + dk_z'^2) \lambda_c'^2$$

The invariance means: $ds' = ds$, and the invariance equation is then written:

$$dn^2 c^2/v^2 - (dk_x^2 + dk_y^2 + dk_z^2) \lambda_c^2 = dn^2 c'^2/v'^2 - (dk_x'^2 + dk_y'^2 + dk_z'^2) \lambda_c'^2$$

Conclusion

The above reasoning has been done thanks to the various definitions, which were not existing, or still in an embryonic state, at the time of Einstein (1879-1955). However, the result is interesting because in the equation about the invariance, the two concepts of time and space are replaced by wavelengths and frequencies, which are phenomena. As Einstein thought, space and time don't seem necessary. This return of phenomena in mathematical modeling to the detriment of concepts must now be evaluated in order to decide if it is beneficial or not.

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